

**EXPLORING THE FACTOR STRUCTURE OF THE EXERCISE DEPENDENCE
SCALE-REVISED AMONG FILIPINO FITNESS ENTHUSIASTS IN
METRO MANILA, PHILIPPINES**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 9

Pages: 1111-1120

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2418

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13850760

Manuscript Accepted: 09-02-2024

Exploring the Factor Structure of the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised among Filipino Fitness Enthusiasts in Metro Manila, Philippines

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to verify the stability of the seven-factor structure of the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised (EDS-R). The EDS-R by Hausenblas and Symons-Down (2002) is one of the commonly used measures to assess exercise dependence. This study was conducted to examine the factor structure of the EDS-R and determine if the seven-factor model is supported in the Filipino context. Additionally, this study aimed to evaluate if the seven criteria or dimensions of the EDS-R represent seven distinct factors as operationalized by the Diagnostic Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder IV-TR (DSM-IV-TR). The English version of this questionnaire was administered to 373 Filipino fitness enthusiasts (224 males and 149 females) aged 18 years old and above. Since the seven factors were assumed to be correlated, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) using parallel analysis and maximum likelihood method with oblique rotation (promax) were used. Using Bartlett's test of sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test, the correlation matrix was not random, and the test was found to be factorable. The KMO test also indicated adequate sampling yielding .92. The cut-off point of the minimum residuals factor analysis was set at .40. Fit indices, parallel analysis, eigenvalue greater than 1, and the scree test were compared to determine the number of factors and assess the adequacy of the model. Parallel analysis and the maximum likelihood estimation were used to determine the number of factors. Results suggest that the seven-factor model was not supported. Parallel analysis supported a six-factor model which accounted for 64.5% of the variance. Factor loadings range from .41 to .97, except for Item 12 which has a factor loading of .29). Although the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) for the six-factor model is lower than .95, it is still better compared to the seven-factor model or the two-factor model. Since most of the correlations between the factors in the six-factor model range from moderate ($r = .49$) to high ($r = .74$), the three-factor model's utility was supported. Only Factor 2 and Factor 5 are weakly correlated ($r = .26$). Despite this, the results suggest that the six-factor model better reflects the experiences of exercise dependence among Filipino fitness enthusiasts.

Keywords: *exercise, exercise dependence, factor structure, exercise dependence scale*

Introduction

Generally, research shows that exercise results in improvement in mental health and is considered as a part of a healthy lifestyle (Mikkelsen et al., 2017; White et al., 2017). The growing number of individuals with gym memberships or those who frequent the gym is an indication that more and more people are motivated to be physically fit and healthy around the globe. But while the lack of regular physical activity can be a barrier to a healthier lifestyle, too much or excessive exercise may pose some serious concerns. Excessive exercising may lead to exercise dependence, a psychological phenomenon that has been operationalized as a multidimensional maladaptive pattern of exercise, leading to clinical impairment or distress (Hausenblas & Symons Downs, 2002). This definition was set based on the DSM-IV criteria for substance use which Hausenblas and Symons Downs used as a framework and which conceptualized exercise addiction or exercise dependence as "a physical activity that is extreme in frequency and duration, relatively resistant to change, and is often associated with an irresistible impulse to continue exercise despite injury, illness, fatigue, or other personal demands" (APA, 1994; APA, 2013). Exercise dependence is characterized by the presence of three or more of the following seven criteria: withdrawal, continuance, tolerance, lack of control, reduction in other activities, time, and intention effects. Withdrawal refers to characteristic withdrawal symptoms from exercise (e.g. fatigue) or the same (or closely related) amount of exercise taken to relieve or avoid withdrawal symptoms. Withdrawal can also be manifested by anhedonia, irritability, depression, and anxiety when the individual suddenly reduces or stops exercise (Chen, 2016). Continuance refers to continued exercise despite knowledge of having a persistent or recurrent physical or psychological problem that is likely to have been caused or exacerbated by the exercise. Tolerance refers to increased amounts of exercise to achieve the desired effect or a diminished effect occurs with continued use of the same amount of exercise. The individual increases the amount of exercise to reduce craving (Chen, 2016). Lack of control refers to persistent desire or unsuccessful effort to cut down or control exercise. Reduction in other activities refers to social, occupational, or recreational activities that are given up or reduced because of exercise. Time refers to a great deal of time is spent in activities necessary to obtain exercise and intention effect refers to exercise is often taken in larger amounts or over a longer period than was intended. These seven criteria correspond to the seven dimensions of the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised. There is a growing interest in exercise dependence since some people were shown to become addicted to physical activity (Schreiber & Hausenblas, 2015).

This study is significant for certain reasons. Some studies conducted on exercise dependence determined the prevalence of exercise dependence in a particular population (i.e. Uz, 2016), while others correlated exercise dependence to other variables or clinical conditions, such as eating disorders (Harris, et al., 2015; Zeulner, et al., 2016) and self-esteem (Ertl, et al., 2017), this study focused on validation of one of the most common scales to measure exercise dependence. Scale development and validation are critical processes

in research. Scale validation is a necessary process to ensure that the scale measures what it is supposed to measure and that it is a reliable tool to measure a particular construct or psychological phenomenon. Since several definitions and assessments of exercise dependence exist (e.g. Exercise Addiction Inventory (EAI) developed by Griffiths et al., 2005; Exercise Dependence Questionnaire (EDQ) developed by Ogden et al., 2009), we believe that it is necessary to verify the stability and utility of the Exercise Dependence Scale in the Filipino context. This study will add to the knowledge and theory building on exercise and exercise dependence. As definitions change, the understanding of the nature of exercise dependence also advances. As of present, there are no specific criteria for exercise dependence in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Disorders-IV (DSM-IV) and in its most recent edition, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5), wherein only gambling was included as a behavioral addiction.

Furthermore, we are interested in The Exercise Dependence Scale because it has been used by previous studies on exercise dependence in different settings and contexts and it has been translated in different languages (Downs et al., 2004; Allegre & Therme, 2008; Lindwall & Palmeira, 2009; Sicilia & González-Cutre, 2011; Costa et al., 2012; Mónok et al., 2012; Parastatidou et al., 2012; Alchieri et al., 2015; Müller et al., 2013; Shin & You, 2015; Uz & Bavli, 2016, Deflandre & Kassabian, 2022). The frequent use of this scale has prompted numerous studies of structural validation using confirmatory analysis (Deflandre & Kassabian, 2022). There is also a dearth of local literature about exercise dependence in the Philippine setting. Most of the studies conducted on exercise dependence were conducted in Western settings, hence, there is a need to explore exercise dependence in the local setting to bridge this data gap.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study was to examine the factor structure of the 21-item English version of the Exercise Dependence Scale Revised by Hausenblas and Symons-Down (2002). Specifically, this study aimed to verify the stability of the seven-factor structure of the EDS-R and examine if the seven-factor model is supported in the Filipino context. The scale was administered to 373 Filipino (224 males and 149 females) fitness enthusiasts or regular exercisers aged 18 years old and above who are members of fitness centers in Metro Manila, Philippines

Literature Review

Exercise Dependence and the Exercise Dependence Scale

The duration, frequency, and intensity of different forms of physical activity needed by the body varies between people and across age groups. The World Health Organization (2018) has recommended that for children and adolescents aged 5-17 years, they should do at least 60 minutes of moderate to vigorous-intensity physical activity daily, and should include activities that strengthen muscle and bone, at least 3 times per week. Adults aged 18–64 should do at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity throughout the week or do at least 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity throughout the week, or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity. Adults aged 65 years and older should do at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity throughout the week, or at least 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity physical activity throughout the week, or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity. Exercising more frequently and for longer hours than recommended may lead to excessive exercise or exercise dependence.

Exercise dependence is present in both athletes and non-athletes. Uz (2016) found exercise dependence symptoms in non-athletes who exercise regularly. Significant differences were found between groups in terms of weekly exercise frequency and exercise dependence. A positive but low correlation was observed between exercise dependence scores and weekly exercise frequency and daily exercise duration suggesting that time spent exercising is associated with symptoms of exercise dependence. The findings suggest that exercise frequency and duration among non-athletes or sedentariness may lead to exercise dependence symptoms.

Eating disorders and exercise addiction were also found to be correlated. Zeulner et al. (2016), assessed the prevalence of eating disorders and exercise dependence among 1,031 German endurance athletes. Results showed that 18.9% of the athletes were at risk for developing an eating disorder and 2.7% had the potential to develop exercise addiction.

There was no significant gender difference concerning developing eating disorders and exercise addiction indicating that both genders were equally at-risk.

However, the prevalence of exercise dependence in Western settings was found to be relatively small. Lichtenstein and Jensen (2016) found that 5% among CrossFitters were found to be exercise-dependent and that younger males had higher risks. Findings also suggest that CrossFitters have a higher risk for exercise addiction. Among nonathletes who exercise regularly, 1.6% were at risk (Uz, 2016). As indicated by these studies, the prevalence of exercise dependence is small and rare. Nevertheless, this number is not insignificant since it is often associated with other clinical conditions.

There has been a growing interest in exercise dependence over the past years. In the Philippines, this topic has not been explored widely, hence, there is a need to explore exercise dependence in the local setting to bridge this data gap.

This study aimed to examine the factor structure of the EDS-R and to determine if the seven criteria of exercise dependence as operationalized by the DSM IV represents seven distinct factors among Filipino fitness enthusiasts.

Examining the Factor Structure of the Exercise Dependence Scale

The Exercise Dependence Scale operationalizes exercise dependence based on the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-IV (DSM-IV) criteria for substance dependence. Since DSM-IV does not have specific criteria for exercise dependence, the criteria for substance dependence were used as the framework (Hausenblas & Symons Downs, 2002). The EDS-R is a 21-item test and can be administered in individual and or group settings. It has been used with respondents 18 years and older. Participants indicate their responses on a Likert scale of 1-6 with 1 (never) being the lowest and 6 (always) being the highest. A higher score indicates more exercise dependence symptoms. It takes approximately five minutes to complete.

Validation studies of the EDS revealed acceptable test-retest and internal consistency reliability, and content and concurrent validity (Hausenblas & Symons Downs, 2010). Both exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses also indicated a good fit for EDS. Results showed that individuals who were found to be at risk for exercise dependence reported more strenuous exercise, perfectionism, and higher self-efficacy compared to the non-dependent groups.

Currently, the scale has an English version (Downs et al., 2004), French version (Allegre & Therme, 2008), Swedish and Portuguese versions (Lindwall & Palmeira, 2009), Spanish version (Sicilia & González-Cutre, 2011), Italian version (Costa et al., 2012), Hungarian version (Mónok et al., 2012), Greek version (Parastatidou et al., 2012), Brazilian Portuguese version (Alchieri et al., 2015), German version (Müller et al., 2013) and Korean version (Shin & You, 2015).

The Spanish version of the EDS-R was found to have acceptable fit indices: $\chi^2(168, N = 531) = 489.98, p = .001, \chi^2/df = 2.91, CFI = .94, IFI = .94, RMSEA = .060$ (90% CI = .054 - .066), SRMR = .045 (Sicilia & Gonzalez-Cutre, 2011). The psychometric properties of this version were examined through descriptive analyses, construct validity, confirmatory factor analysis (CFI), analysis of factor invariance across age groups, and analysis of internal consistency using Cronbach's Alpha.

The standardized regression weights of the items ranged between .46 and .89 and were statistically significant ($p < .001$), and satisfactory error variance was obtained. The correlations among the seven factors ranged between .32 and .84, suggesting moderate to high correlations. The analysis of internal consistency revealed Cronbach's Alpha values of .85 for Withdrawal, .81 for Continuance, .73 for Tolerance, .78 for Lack of control, .68 for Reduction in other activities, .84 for Time, and .83 for Intention effects. Consistency for the global value of exercise dependence was .92. Sport center users who practice for more than three days per week had higher scores in all subscales of the EDS-R than the group practicing with a frequency of three days or fewer. The findings of the study provided reliability and validity for the EDS-R in a Spanish context.

The EDS was also correlated with other measures of exercise dependence. Correlation between the EDS and the Exercise Addiction Inventory (EAI) by Griffiths et al., was found to be high ($r = .79$) (Freimuth, et al., 2011). Confirmatory Factor Analysis also indicated a good fit for both EAI and EDS. The results supported EDS as a valid and reliable assessment tool for exercise addiction.

In the validation studies conducted on the EDS, varied structural validation techniques have been used. Several studies conducted either exploratory factor analysis or confirmatory factor analysis, or both (Downs et al., 2004; Allegre & Therme, 2008; Lindwall & Palmeira, 2009; Sicilia & González-Cutre, 2011; Costa et al., 2012; Mónok et al., 2012; Parastatidou et al., 2012; Alchieri et al., 2015; Shin & You, 2015; Pujals et al., 2018; and Deflandre & Kassabian, 2022). While CFA attempts to confirm hypotheses EFA tries to uncover complex patterns by exploring the dataset (Child, 2006). According to researchers, EFA has the following objectives (Pett et al., 2003; Thompson, 2004):

1. Reduce the number of variables
2. Examine the structure or relationship between variables
3. Detection and assessment of unidimensionality of a theoretical construct
4. Evaluate the construct validity of a scale, test, or instrument
5. Development of parsimonious (simple) analysis and interpretation
6. Addresses multicollinearity (two or more variables that are correlated)
7. Used to develop theoretical constructs
8. Used to prove/disprove proposed theories

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is a data reduction technique used to regroup variables into a limited set of clusters based on shared characteristics (common variance) (Yong & Pierce, 2013). EFA aims to identify the common factors (dimensions) that explain the order and structure of measured variables (Watkins, 2018).

The main objective of this study – to examine the factor structure of the 21-item English version of the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised and to verify the stability of the seven-factor model of the EDS-R and if this is supported in the Filipino context – is more consistent with the aims of EFA than CFA.

Although some studies support the seven-factor model of the EDS, other studies propose other alternatives: Kern (2007) rejected a one-factor model on the French version, while Allegre and Therme (2008) rejected a first-order six-factor model. These studies suggest the necessity to further examine its factorial validity.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design of the present study was quantitative. It involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature, composition, or processes of phenomena. Specifically, the present study utilized a survey as the data collection method. Survey provided a quantitative description of trends, attitudes, or opinions of a population by studying a sample of that population using questionnaires for data collection. Data collection was done through the administration of a pen-and-paper questionnaire.

Respondents

The research was conducted at the health, fitness, and wellness centers that provide services for slimming, health, fitness, and beauty care which has a main office in Alabang, Muntinlupa City. It operates in twenty-five (25) centers located in Metro Manila, Cebu, Subic, and Bangkok, Thailand, and has over 500,000 fitness enthusiasts. The participants were regular members of the fitness and wellness centers in Alabang, Muntinlupa City, and SM Megamall in Mandaluyong City, but they reside in various places in Metro, Manila.

The sample consisted of 373 fitness enthusiasts recruited through purposive sampling. The majority of the respondents are 18-40 years old with $n = 261$ (70%), 97 (26%) respondents are 41-64 years old and 15 (4%) are 65 years old and older. More than half of the respondents are male with 60.1% ($n=224$) while women comprised 39.9% of the sample ($n=149$). The dominance of males in gyms is consistent with the data from the Health and Social Care Information Centre (2011) in England which reported that only 29% of UK women were achieving recommended levels of physical activity compared to 39% of males (Daigle, 2011). Most of the respondents have a normal BMI (56.3%), followed by those who are overweight (31.9%), obese class I (8.8%), underweight (1.6%) and obese class II (1.3%). Majority of the respondents exercised for 61-120 minutes (63%). Nonprobability, purposive sampling was utilized to select fitness enthusiasts who satisfied the following criteria:

- (1) 18 years old and above;
- (2) enrolled in the Fitness Clubs for at least six months (not necessarily lifetime members); and
- (3) have attended sessions regularly for the past six months

Non-probability, purposive sampling was used to determine the sample and sample size. Each participant was approached and asked to complete two self-administered questionnaires: a personal data sheet that contains their demographic profiles and the EDS-R. This was done in the presence of one of the researchers to clarify any misunderstood item. They were regular exercisers, approached before or after training sessions. Informed consent was sought, and the nature and procedures of the study were explained to the participants. Their rights were emphasized, and they were reminded that their participation was entirely voluntary. The fitness enthusiasts may or may not have extended physical activity inside or outside their wellness centers. After the administration of the questionnaires, the participants were thanked and given the opportunity to ask questions about the study. They were also given a small token of appreciation.

Instrument

The first part of the questionnaire determined the demographic profile of fitness enthusiasts which included some personal information from the participants. The second part of the questionnaire is the 21-item English version of the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised (EDS-R) by Heather A. Hausenblas and Danielle Symons Downs (2004). It provides the following information:

- Mean overall score of exercise dependence symptoms;
- Differentiates between:
 - At-risk for exercise dependence,
 - Nondependent-symptomatic, and
 - Nondependent-asymptomatic.
- Specifies whether individuals have evidence of:
 - Physiological dependence; or
 - No physiological dependence.

The EDS-R is a 21-item test which operationalizes exercise dependence as a multidimensional maladaptive pattern of exercise, leading to clinically significant impairment or distress, as manifested by three or more of the following criteria: tolerance, withdrawal, intention effect, lack of control, time, reduction in other activities, and continuance. It can be administered in individual and group settings and has been used with respondents 18 years and older. Participants indicate their responses on a Likert scale of 1-6 with 1 (never) being the lowest and 6 (always) being the highest. A higher score indicates more exercise dependent symptoms. It takes approximately five minutes to complete.

The proposed scoring procedure for the EDS-R is computer-based which allows for immediate and accurate scoring. The computer scoring of the EDS-R is based on the Statistic Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). A syntax file has been developed (as indicated in the Manual) by the authors that enable immediate feedback to the EDS-R responses once the items are entered into SPSS. The syntax

enables:

Computing a total and subscale mean scores for Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised. A higher score indicates more exercise dependent symptoms.

Categorizing participants into either at-risk for exercise dependence, nondependent-symptomatic, or nondependent-asymptomatic groups. The categorization into one of the three groups is generated by a scoring manual that consists of flow chart decision rules, in which items or combinations of items determine if an individual would be classified in the dependent, symptomatic, or asymptomatic range on each of the 7 DSM criteria. Individuals who are classified into the dependent range on three or more of the DSM criteria are classified as exercise dependent. The dependent range is operationalized as indicating a score of 5 or 6 for that item. Individuals who scored in the 3 to 4 range are classified as symptomatic. These individuals may theoretically be considered at-risk for exercise dependence. Finally, individuals who score in the 1-2 range are classified as asymptomatic.

The EDS was found to have acceptable test-retest and internal consistency reliability, and content and concurrent validity (Hausenblas & Symons Downs, 2010). Confirmatory Factor Analysis also indicated good fit for EDS (Monok, et al., 2012).

Procedure

Data collection was done pre-pandemic (late 2019 to early 2020). Before the administration of the EDS-R, permission was first obtained from the managers of the fitness clubs. Informed consent was obtained from each participant before inclusion in the study informing them of their rights to withdraw from the study at any point during the data collection process. The nature and purpose of the study were explained, and they were assured of anonymity and confidentiality. The EDS-R was administered to fitness enthusiasts who satisfy the criteria for inclusion.

Collection of data was done through the use of the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised (2004). The researchers were granted permission by the developer of the instrument to use the Exercise Dependence Scale in this study. Information regarding the respondents' demographic profile such as age, sex, BMI, exercise frequency, and exercise duration were also obtained. For some fitness enthusiasts who only included their height and weight, their BMI were computed by the researchers.

Data Analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis, specifically, parallel analysis and maximum likelihood extraction method with oblique rotation (promax) was used to verify the factor structure of the 21-item English version of the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised. As recommended by Williams et al., (2010), this study was guided by the five-step EFA protocol:

Step 1: Is the data suitable for factor analysis?

Step 2: How will the factors be extracted?

Step 3: What criteria will assist in determining factor extraction?

Step 4: Selection of Rotational Method

Step 5: Interpretation

Bartlett's test of sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin statistic were used to ensure that the correlation matrix was not random. Univariate skewness, kurtosis, and the Shapiro-Wilk test statistics were also computed to ensure normality in the data. The cut-off point of the minimum residuals factor analysis was set at .40. Fit indices, parallel analysis, eigenvalue greater than 1, and the scree test were used to determine the number of factors and assess the adequacy of the model. The EFA was conducted in JAMOV version 2.4.11.

The correlation matrix of the 21 items was examined to ensure that the correlations between the same construct's indicators are significant. Fit indices were analyzed: the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), and the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI). RMSEA with values of 0.06 and TLI superior to 0.90 indicate a good model fit and TLI value superior to 0.95 indicate an excellent model fit (Bentler, 1990; Hu and Bentler, 1998).

Ethical Considerations

This study observed high ethical standards. The study ensured that all participants provided informed consent before their involvement. Participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. To safeguard autonomy, participants were given clear and comprehensive information in a language they could easily understand, and they were encouraged to ask questions to ensure they fully understood the implications of their participation.

To protect the confidentiality of participants, stringent measures were put in place to safeguard participant privacy. Data was anonymized at the point of collection and maintained throughout the study, with unique identifiers replacing personally identifiable information. All electronic data was stored securely in a Google Drive that is restricted and only authorized research team members has access. Physical copies of data were kept in locked storage to prevent unauthorized access.

This study was designed with careful attention to minimizing any potential harm. Participants were informed in advance about the nature of the questions they would be asked and contact information for counseling and or psychological services were provided. Participants were also informed that they could speak with a member of the research team if they needed immediate support. Protecting the well-being of participants was the topmost priority of this study.

The study was guided by the principle of beneficence: the potential benefits to participants and society outweighed the minimal risks involved.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary analysis was conducted to check the assumption of normality. Univariate skewness is not ≥ 2.0 and kurtosis is not ≥ 7.0 , indicating that the data is relatively normal (Curran, et al., 1996). The p-value of the Shapiro-Wilk test is also greater than .05. To explore the factorial structure of the English version of the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised (EDS), all 21 items of the instrument were subjected to an exploratory factor analysis maximum likelihood method with oblique rotation (promax) because the factors are assumed to be correlated to some degree and to allow for these intercorrelations to emerge (Gorsuch, 1983; Gaskin & Happell, 2014). Bartlett's test of sphericity (Bartlett, 1950) was used to ensure that the correlation matrix was not random and the KMO statistic was required to be above a minimum of .50 (Kaiser, 1974). The cut-off point of the minimum residuals factor analysis was set at .40. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test indicated adequate sampling yielding .92, which also suggests that the data is suited for factor analysis (Kaiser, 1974). Bartlett's test of sphericity $\chi^2 (373) = 4933, p < .001$, indicates that correlation structure is adequate and therefore suitable for data reduction techniques.

The correlation matrix of the 21 items was examined to ensure that the correlations between the same construct's indicators were significant. All 21 items have correlations ranging from $r = .20$ to $.71$. Reliability analysis resulted in Cronbach's $\alpha = .94$. Fit indices, parallel analysis, eigenvalue greater than 1, and the scree test were used to determine the number of factors and assess the adequacy of the model.

Factor extraction and Rotation

Minimum residuals with oblique rotation (promax) are the method of extraction and rotation used in the initial analysis since the factors are assumed to be correlated. Promax was used because it results in greater correlations among the factors and achieves a simple structure (Gorsuch, 1983). Kaiser's criterion (eigenvalue greater than 1) was also used for comparison.

Factor loadings and Cross-loadings

Factor loadings range from 0.41 to 0.97. Only one item was below the cut-off point of 0.4: Item 12: I think about exercise when I should be concentrating on school. Five items cross-loaded on other factors: Item 19: I choose to exercise so that I can get out of spending time with..., Item 6: I spend most of my free time exercising, Item 7: I exercise longer than I intend, Item 15: I exercise to avoid feeling tense, Item 9: I exercise when injured. Uniqueness variance range from .14 to .57. Factor loadings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. *Exploratory Factor Analysis of the Items of the EDS-R using Parallel Analysis and Maximum Likelihood with Oblique Rotation*

	Factor						Uniqueness
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
I would rather exercise than spend time with family/friends	0.774						0.440
I spend a lot of time exercising	0.738						0.455
A great deal of my time is spent exercising	0.706						0.383
I choose to exercise so that I can get out of spending time wit	0.653					0.229	0.443
I spend most of my free time exercising	0.576	0.257					0.454
I think about exercise when I should be concentrating on school	0.288						0.574
I exercise longer than I expect		0.968					0.140
I exercise longer than I plan		0.723					0.239
I exercise longer than I intend	0.221	0.412		0.254			0.418
I continually increase my exercise frequency to achieve the des			0.918				0.234
I continually increase my exercise duration to achieve the desi			0.753				0.315
I continually increase my exercise intensity to achieve the des			0.731				0.407
I am unable to reduce how long I exercise				0.893			0.256
I am unable to reduce how often I exercise				0.838			0.309
I am unable to reduce how intense I exercise				0.546			0.402

I exercise to avoid feeling anxious		0.854	0.272
I exercise to avoid feeling irritable		0.847	0.375
I exercise to avoid feeling tense	0.228	0.736	0.253
I exercise despite persistent physical problems			0.940
I exercise despite recurring physical problems			0.707
I exercise when injured	0.249		0.573

Note. 'Maximum likelihood' extraction method was used in combination with a 'promax' rotation

The parallel analysis resulted with six factors: Factor 1 with five items and accounted for 14.31% of the variance; Factor 2 with three items and accounted for 10.76% of the variance; and Factor 3 with three items and accounted for 9.95% of the variance; Factor 4 with three items and accounted for 9.90% of the variance; Factor 5 with three items and accounted for 9.80% of the variance; Factor 6 with three items and accounted for 9.78% of the variance. Item 12 was discarded because its factor loading is below .4. The six-factor model accounted for 64.5% of the variance. The percentage of variance explained by each factor and the cumulative percentage is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Cumulative Factor Loadings

Factor	SS Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.01	14.31	14.3
2	2.26	10.76	25.1
3	2.09	9.95	35.0
4	2.08	9.90	44.9
5	2.06	9.80	54.7
6	2.05	9.78	64.5

Factor naming and interpretation

A closer analysis of the items and a review of literature influenced the labels given to the factors/ dimensions. The items in Factor 1 seem to describe spending a lot of time and preoccupation with exercising. Upon closer inspection of the items, they seem to have one common denominator – time. It is interesting to note that the items in the five criteria in the original scale – Intention effect, Lack of control, Time, Reduction in other activities, and Continuance – imply a longer period spent on exercising. This factor can be labeled Time. Items in Factor 2 seem to suggest exercising more than what was planned or intended. This factor may be labeled Intention. Items in Factor 3 seem to suggest the need for longer duration, increased frequency, and intensity spent in exercising. This may still be labelled as Tolerance. Items in Factor 4 seems to describe an inability to control the time spent exercising. This can be labeled as Lack of Control, similar to the original scale. Items in Factor 5 seems to describe the need to exercise to avoid the negative effects of not exercising. This can be labeled Positive reward. Items in Factor 6 seems to describe continuing to exercise despite pain and injury. The label Continuance can be retained for this factor.

Comparing the proposed six-factor structure to the original seven-factor structure, only the subscale Reduction in other activities was not supported, consistent with the results of previous studies (e.g. Deflandre & Kassabian, 2022).

Model fit

The cumulative percentage of variance is higher in the six-factor model (64.5%) than in the two-factor model suggested by the eigenvalue greater than 1 (Kaiser’s criterion) method (49.2%). Even if the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) for both models is lower than .95, the TLI of the six-factor model is better than the TLI of the two-factor model (.90 vs .72). A good model fit is if the TLI is at least .90 and excellent fit if greater than .95 (Bentler, 1990; Hu and Bentler, 1998). The RMSEA of the six-factor model (.07) is better than that of the two-factor model (.129). An RMSEA of at least .06 indicates a good fit (Bentler, 1990; Hu and Bentler, 1998).

Most of the correlations between the factors in the six-factor model range from moderate ($r = .49$) to high ($r = .74$), hence, the three-factor model’s utility was supported. Only Factor 2 and Factor 5 are weakly correlated ($r = .26$). The scree test resulted in a one-factor structure but this was not supported by the other fit indices. Although it appears that both the six-factor model and the two-factor model are more parsimonious than the original seven-factor model, the inconsistencies in the fit indices suggest the need for more study. Fit indices for the parallel analysis and Kaiser’s criterion are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. Model Fit Measures (Parallel Analysis)

RMSEA	RMSEA 90% CI		TLI	BIC	Model Test		
	Lower	Upper			χ^2	df	p
0.0767	0.0675	0.0865	0.901	-270	317	99	<.001

Table 4. Model Fit Measures (Eigenvalue greater than 1)

RMSEA	RMSEA 90% CI		TLI	BIC	Model Test		
	Lower	Upper			χ^2	df	p
0.129	0.122	0.136	0.724	213	1214	169	<.001

Conclusions

The present study attempted to identify the smallest number of factors (dimensions) that can parsimoniously explain the covariation among a set of variables. Using parallel analysis, eigenvalue greater than 1, and scree plot to determine the model that best fits the experiences of the Filipino sample, a six-factor model and a two-factor model emerged, with the six-factor model accounting for most variance. The results of this study failed to support the seven-factor model of the EDS-R as operationalized by the DSM IV. This study also supported the concerns on one of the subscales of the original seven-factor model, Reduction in other activities, as this was not supported by the parallel analysis conducted. Hence, this factor/ dimension requires a thorough revision. Future research may focus on developing a scale for exercise dependence based on a different model to better reflect the experiences of Filipino fitness enthusiasts.

This study has its limitations. In terms factorial validity, only exploratory factor analysis was conducted. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct confirmatory factor analysis on the seven-factor, six-factor and two-factor model for further validation. Also, while a sample size of 373 is robust, there could be a limitation regarding how representative the sample is of the broader population of Filipino fitness enthusiasts. Since majority of the participants are males and within the 18-40 age range, the findings may not generalize to all fitness enthusiasts in the Philippines. Additionally, since the study relied on self-reported data, this could introduce biases such as social desirability bias, where participants might overestimate or underestimate their exercise behaviors to present themselves in a more favorable light. Although the Exercise Dependence Scale-Revised (EDS-R) is a validated tool, its applicability and reliability in the Filipino context might present a limitation. The study may need to ensure that the tool accurately captures the nuances of exercise dependence among Filipino fitness enthusiasts. Future researchers could consider developing or adapting tools that are more culturally specific to the Filipino context, ensuring they accurately capture the constructs being measured.

Insights

This study underscores the importance of evaluating the factor structure of assessment measures or screening tools like the EDS-R to ensure their suitability and utility in measuring certain constructs such as exercise dependence. Since the findings do not support the current seven-factor model of the EDS-R, a reconceptualization of exercise dependence may be deemed necessary. The results suggest a need for further refinement of the tool.

Engaging in this study has provided us with profound insights into both the complexity and the necessity of rigorous tool validation in psychological assessment. The process of exploring the factor structure of an instrument has deepened our appreciation for the meticulous work that goes into ensuring such tools are both reliable and valid.

Conducting this study with Filipino fitness enthusiasts as sample suggests that exercise dependence might manifest differently across various populations. Cultural and demographic considerations are important in psychological assessment. This research suggests a need for a more inclusive and representative assessment tools for diverse and culturally different populations.

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